

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF CATTLE IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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Annotation. In the article our country Animal husbandry in networks cattle breeding infrastructure activities diversification and efficiency increase ways discussion done Analysis as a result cattle breeding infrastructure farm of enterprises economic efficiency level increased to go analysis done

Keywords: Infrastructure, diversification, efficiency, specialization, consumer, market, farmer farm, farmer farm, price

Enter The world population number yearly growth tendency preserved remaining in the circumstances people animal husbandry products with medical norms level provide issue as relevant remains Therefore, industrial progress reached countries animal husbandry networks organize to make, to place and specialization based on intensive development, people ecological clean cattle products with provide this countries Agrarian of politics priority from directions one as is considered. After all, animal husbandry productivity increase basically science in animal husbandry and of technologies development depends to be cattle goods feeding, zooveterinary services, livestock goods health in the field scientific, technological developments current reach and breeding their work expand and network economic and financial levers through support necessity is increasing.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY Cattle breeding stable development, animal husbandry products work release efficiency increase such as row problems CIS countries from scientists Arzumanyan Ye.A., Kozaev IS, Nechaev VI, Artyomova Ye.I., Dankvert AS, Gryadov SI2 and another many scientists scientific research take they went

Our republic conditions animal husbandry networks development and efficiency increase problems Mallabaev TS, Hakimov RH, Khushmatov NS, Yuldashev A., Kusharov ZK, Khushmatov UN, Omarov T. and another a number of scientists scientific works dedicated.

RESULTS. In the future cattle breeding infrastructure subjects development and they are activities diversification of doing main directions founding; in the republic cotton, grain, polys products and food crops lands volume and of head of cattle change cases account received without meat and milk products work until 2030 has been forecast parameters work exit

DISCUSSION Our Republic village in the farm take going economic of reforms next stages farmer farms development, they activities diversification, that is from the composition wide network income work release level deliver regarding to them one row benefits, reliefs is being given. For example, Tax in accordance with Article 367 of the Code new organize done farmer farms state from the list past from the day starting from two year for a period of time the only one land tax from paying free done From this except Uzbekistan Republic President of October 10, 2017 "Farmer, farmer farms and homestead land owners activities more development according to organizational measures on" in the decision PQ -3318 farmer,

peasant farms and homestead land of the owners wholesale consumers , that's it including preparation , re work and export doer organizations , agricultural companies , trade enterprises with product delivered to give on the market administration with while cultivated the product directly in the market retail sell about contracts structure systematic respectively organize reach to practice current is being done . Also a village in the farm legal , economic , financial , agrotechnical and another issues according to consulting service , product work release , purchase do , re work , sale , supply and service show according to farmer , peasant farms and homestead land of the owners another organizations with of cooperation different forms organize reach and expansion , this in the field advanced foreign experiences current reach and another one row tasks mean caught Next in years while farmer to farms one row benefits system current reach according to laws and legality documents addition and changes is being entered .

To livestock specialized farms state by support , population good quality animal husbandry products with provide developed countries from experiences come out , livestock products the most high and the most lower prices designation to the goal according to it would be . Because most of them animal husbandry products , that's it including meat and milk work output is low yield or damage with working activity type that it was for many in the states in subsidy standing field being is counted . Cattle breeding is also known in our republic basically damage seeing working or less profitable network is considered That's why for to animal husbandry specialized village economy enterprises , farmers and farmer of farms income increase and they are in the activity innovative technique and technologies current reach for to them preferential loans separation , insurance payments partially state from the budget pay to give and subsidies separation , as well as in the country village economy of products internal in the market prices in order put in order to quota and tariffs installation to the goal according to As you know , cattle breeding is also in our republic basically damage seeing working or less profitable network is considered That's why for to animal husbandry specialized village economy enterprises , farmers and farmer of farms income increase and they are in the activity innovative technique and technologies current reach for to them preferential loans separation , insurance payments partially state from the budget to pay and subsidies separation , as well as in the country village economy of products internal in the market prices in order put in order to quota and tariffs installation to the goal according to Research as shown , for example , by release infrastructure subjects by displayed services village economy in networks crops and cattle goods care , product cultivation efficiency in raising separately role plays and this to the field directed - gan investments in 4-6 years himself covers Work release infrastructure - masi objects efficiency to determine for the following from the formula profit recommendation is done , that is :

$$Sin = PMqx / INif$$

this here : **Sin** - work release infrastructure subject of activity efficiency , soum / soum ; **PMqx** - a village economy conclusion (gross) product , soum ; **INif** - infrastructure subject organize to do spent investment size , soum .

It is known that cattle breeding network in development including zoovete-rinaria service separately role plays Research show , livestock products grower to farms this service types with depends special technique , equipment and another equipment delivered to give , in the population cattle goods artificial escape and another services show scope and relevance from

per year increased is going That's it because , in our opinion , veterinary medicine service organize to reach whole one to the system to bring and of this for republic and his regions in the section specialized manage structures basis put , this institute through him financing and control to do state by done increase to the goal according to

Conclusion . In the Republic of cattle productivity demand level it's not . Of this main reasons to the line breeder of goods decreased gone and of the population artificial to fertilize has been negative relationship and pedigree the seeds delivered in giving monopoly situation , pedigree goods of seeds poor quality , goods artificial fertilization centers and of specialists lack of it , exaggeration of technology efficient that it is not , in places farmer and farmer in farms artificial fertilization their work done increase for qualified of experts lack of such as problems solution reach measures done increase it is necessary

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